

Local Government in Ethiopia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Zemelak Ayele

CFGs - Centre for Federalism and Governance Studies
Addis Ababa University

Partners

**eurac
research**

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw
University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University
Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Ethiopia is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

Addis Ababa University: Zemelak Ayele
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Daggy J Ali_Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Ethiopia.....	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Ethiopia: An Introduction	8
2.2. <i>Autonomy of Local Governments</i>	11
2.3. <i>Sanitation and Hygiene Service Delivery in Urban Local Governments: A Federally Integrated Practice</i>	18
2.4. <i>Responsibilities for and Practices of Urban Land Use Planning in the City of Adama</i>	25
2.5. <i>Solid Waste Management in the City of Bahir Dar: A Matter of Capacity and Public Awareness</i> ...	34
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Ethiopia: An Introduction	39
3.2. <i>The Fiscal Equalization Scheme for Woredas</i>	43
3.3. <i>Financing Municipal Services</i>	46
3.4. <i>Financing Healthcare: The Example of the Raya-Kobo District</i>	49
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Ethiopia: An Introduction.....	55
4.2. <i>The Practice of Local Government Creation (Splitting)</i>	57
4.3. <i>Amalgamating Five Special Local Governments into a Single Administrative Zone vs Self-Government Rights of Ethnic Groups in SNNPRS</i>	61
4.4. <i>Splitting Local Government and its (Un)expected Outcomes: The Case of Amhara National Regional State</i>	67
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Ethiopia: An Introduction	73
5.2. <i>Association of Cities/Urban Forum and Urban-Rural Relations</i>	75
5.3. <i>Changing Urban Place Names in Post 2018 Amhara National Regional State: The View from Bahir Dar City</i>	85
5.4. <i>Infrastructure Projects in Addis Ababa: Between Self-Government of the Capital City and Federal Intervention</i>	91
6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Ethiopia: An Introduction	96
6.2. <i>Participation in Urban Water Management Board in Adama/Oromia</i>	99
6.3. <i>Local Governance and Gender in Family Relations</i>	104
6.4. <i>Political Participation Along Ethnic Lines: The City of Dire Dawa</i>	108

People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Ethiopia: An Introduction

Zemelak Ayele, *CFGs – Centre for Federalism and Governance Studies, Addis Ababa University*

Scholars consider local government to be the best level of government for public participation.¹⁶⁸ This mainly because it is relatively small in territorial and population size which makes it effective in allowing public participation. The Ethiopian Constitution also links the establishment of local government with enhancing public participation. Likewise, the District Level Decentralisation Program (DLDP) was implemented with enhancing public participation at the local level. In the policy papers that articulated the need to decentralize powers at the local level it was clearly stated that doing so was imperative to empower local communities to 'participate, negotiate and influence' the decision-making processes concerning local matters. To this effect it was stated that regular local elections would be conducted and that the capacity of local representative councils and other democratic institutions would be strengthened.¹⁶⁹ The decentralization program was also underpinned by the need to create enhanced opportunities for civil society organizations to play an important role in the process of service delivery by facilitating 'interaction, and mobilizing groups and communities to participate in social, economic and political activities' in particular at local level. The need to empower women was also taken as an integral part of this local political reform.¹⁷⁰

Public participation at the local level takes place in two major ways. The first is an indirect one, through the electoral process. Local governments of all tiers have an elected representative council and a parliamentary form of executive. Members of local councils are directly elected by local communities on the basis of a multiparty system. Since the adoption of the 1995 Constitution five local elections have been held (in 1997, 2002, 2008, 2013). The sixth local elections were supposed to be held in May 2018. Due to the political crisis in the country which began in 2015 and the poor security situation, these elections have been postponed indefinitely. Local elections in Ethiopia are not in general viewed as important elections both by political parties and the voters. The opposition parties have never taken part in local election since the adoption of the 1995 Constitution. They often accuse the ruling party of political repression and boycott local elections. The reason for doing so does not however seem to be only the repression by the ruling party. Opposition parties take part in national elections while complaining about political repression. It rather seems that they do not view winning local

¹⁶⁸ See David Beetham, 'Theorising Democracy and Local Governance' in Desmond King and Gerry Stoker (eds), *Rethinking Local Democracy* (Macmillan 1996) 38; Keith Dowding, 'Public Choice and Local Governance' in Desmond King and Gerry Stoker (eds), *Rethinking Local Democracy* (Macmillan 1996) 53; Jaap De Visser, *Developmental Local Government: A Case Study of South Africa* (Intersentia 2005).

¹⁶⁹ Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia Ministry of Finance and Economic Development (MoFED), 'Sustainable Development and Poverty Reduction Programme' (2002).

¹⁷⁰ *ibid.*

elections as important political exercise. There seems to be also a general lack of enthusiasm about local elections among voters. Yet, post-election reports of the National Electoral Board of Ethiopia – the federal agency which is charged with administering elections - claim that voter turnout is around 90 per cent. These numbers are not however to be trusted. The fact is that in every local elections EPRDF's candidates ran in every constituency uncontested and become declared winners. Local elections as means of political participation for local communities seem to have little relevance. And the local voters had little incentive to come out in large number and cast their votes.

The other form of participation is direct participation. Members of local communities are expected to participate during planning process. This especially takes place at the *kebele* level which is, as explained in report section 4 on local government structure, the lowest tier of local government. At the *kebele* level, members of a local community, both individually or through civil society organizations, are entitled to take part in annual planning processes by stating what services need to be given priority in a given fiscal year. The local officials are expected to consider what local communities say should be given priority when drafting annual plan with respect to service delivery. According to Zemelak Ayele, local planning takes place in the following process:

'A *woreda*'s development planning begins with public consultation at village level, the main purpose of which is to identify community problems and prioritise them. The consultations are facilitated by employees of the *kebele*. Civil society organizations (CSOs) are also invited to participate. The CSOs that are invited include traditional associations called *Idir*,¹⁷¹ and others which are engaged in provision of certain basic services including water, sanitation and the like. The community needs that are identified at village level are consolidated at *kebele* level and become a "single *kebele* priority list". The aggregated priorities at *kebele* level are also discussed at a *kebele* general community meeting of the *kebele*'s residents. The *kebele* priority lists are then sent to a *woreda* where the priority lists of the various *kebeles* are consolidated by the *woreda* development planning committee. The aggregate *woreda* priorities are then re-organised on a sectoral basis and passed on to the sectoral office concerned. Based on the priority list, each sectoral office decides on the "intervention areas" and produces a plan. The plan of each sector is then aggregated and "linked to a budget". The plans that are prepared at sectoral level are discussed and negotiated among the various offices with the facilitation of the *Woreda* Planning and Budgeting Desk. The end-result of this negotiation is a single *woreda* plan identifying *woreda* priorities and linking them

¹⁷¹ These are traditional association, often informally established, and meant to serve as self-help association. The assist their members with matters relating to funeral and other social issues.

to budgets. The *woreda* plan is finally submitted to a *woreda* council for approval.¹⁷²

Studies show that direct public consultation at the local level are far from participatory and ineffective in terms of identifying what the public requires to be prioritized. First, public consultations are mainly used for extracting information rather than involving local communities in decision-making. Moreover, whatever members of a local community have said should be prioritized in terms of service delivery are often lost in the process of aggregation and disaggregation by local government experts. Moreover, local officials often ignore what have been identified by local communities as important intervention areas in terms of service delivery and implement their own preferences.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

De Visser J, *Developmental Local Government: A Case Study of South Africa* (Intersentia 2005)

Dowding K, 'Public Choice and Local Governance' in Desmond King and Gerry Stoker (eds), *Rethinking Local Democracy* (Macmillan 1996)

Beetham D, 'Theorising Democracy and Local Governance' in Desmond King and Gerry Stoker (eds), *Rethinking Local Democracy* (Macmillan 1996)

Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia Ministry of Finance and Economic Development (MoFED), 'Sustainable Development and Poverty Reduction Programme' (2002)

Zemelak A, *Local Government in Ethiopia: Advancing Development and Accommodating Ethnic Minorities* (Nomos 2014)

¹⁷² Zemelak Ayele, *Local Government in Ethiopia: Advancing Development and Accommodating Ethnic Minorities* (Nomos 2014).

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

